

The relationship between democracy and revenue of budget

Author's Detail: ¹⁾Ziari-Reza Graduated from Economic Sciences, Department of economic, Science and Research Branch, Islamic Azad University, Tehran, Iran ²⁾ **Rahemi. Hilda:** Student of M.A of economic, Department of economic, Science and Research Branch, Islamic Azad University, Semnan, Iran

Abstract:

Employing panel data method for 21 countries in three groups with high, average and low democracy index, in this article, we investigated the relationship between tax revenues and democracy index. Hence, by using annual data for 2006 to 2011, we estimate three models. Our estimates show the following results:

In high democracy of countries, tax revenues have positive effect on democracy index. In mean democracy countries, tax revenues have positive effect on democracy index, as well as. But other revenues except tax have negative effect on democracy index. These results show citizens have power in decisions countries, if they pay tax to government. And finally, in low democracy of countries. Tax revenues have negative effect on democracy. This result is against of theory. Our interpretation of these results is that the government of such countries have so power and citizens have no interference in the affairs of the country.

Keywords: *democracy index, tax revenue, government*

JEL Classification: *D70, H20, H70*

Introduction:

Research on the relationship between democracy and taxation has yielded

some of the most rich theoretical insights within political science.

Taxation and public spending are major issues in economics and politics. In modern democracies tax revenues need the support of voters in order to be implemented, while at the same time policymakers try to design public policies to please as many voters as possible.

In theatrical research we have that; Raising tax has been shown to create a fiscal contract between citizens and government, mirroring the democratic compact and giving it substance. In other word, the share of tax revenue in total revenue of government is important. Indeed, tax gives citizens a degree of power over their rulers. And tax is thought to lead to demands for democracy, and democracy to legitimate and enhance the efficiency of tax collection. This means that when citizens pay tax, they want to control the country's affairs. Then, according to theatrical research, the relationship between tax and democracy is positive.

The main question is, when the share of tax revenue reduces, and government increases revenues such as natural resources, how it will affect on democracy? We said in previous paragraph, the relationship between tax and democracy is positive, it means that the relationship between other revenue except tax and democracy is not positive. Because, when government has wealth revenue such as natural resource, they do not response for their activities in country. Then the roles of citizens reduce and so democracy reduces in country.

The existing literature on democracy and taxation has primarily considered one direction of causality – that from taxation to democracy. Tilly traced the origin of the revenue imperative, and the development of the state, to the need to go to war (Tilly, 1992). Rulers, needing revenue to fight, had to raise tax, which necessitated the construction of the extractive infrastructure of the state. Brewer showed exactly how the need to collect tax led to the expansion of state capacity in early modern Britain, as the King began developing a Weberian bureaucracy in order to collect excise taxes (Brewer, 1988). This expansion of power increasingly brought the state into conflict with citizens, who demanded concessions, in the form of representation and services, in return for

taxation. They wanted a say in how their money was spent and how this emerging bureaucratic power related to them. The link from taxation to representation has been clearly theoretically explored through these historical processes, and neatly summed up in the demands of American revolutionaries that there be 'no taxation without representation'.

As a number of authors have noted, most states in the developing world are democratizing before they have fully consolidated their statehood (Huntington, 1968; Mansfield & Snyder, 2007; Fukuyama, 2007). While in the West the emergence of representative institutions were in many ways a response to the expansion of the state, both in bureaucratic and fiscal terms, and so came after, many developing countries are democratizing first, before they have constructed 'an orderly administrative powerbase' (Mansfield & Snyder, 2007, p. 59).

In many empirical articles, researchers to test taxes are expected to increase under a democratic regime, to satisfy the needs of the electorate. Boix (2003) suggests that a significant share of the public sector actually depends on the political (democratic) regime in place, which also interacts with the distribution of income, citizens' preferences and economic conditions.

Aidt et al. (2006) find a significant relation between the extension of the voting franchise and the size of government. On the contrary, Mulligan et al. (2004) show that none of the different measures of public spending that they consider (government consumption, education spending and social spending, as a percentage of GDP) is statistically different in democracies and non democracies.⁸ Martin and Plümper (2003) find a U-shaped relationship between the level of democracy and the level of public spending. They argue that for low levels of democracy public spending is high to meet the requests of rents by the elites, while for high levels of democracy public spending is high due to popular demand of public goods.

For medium levels of democracy none of these pressures is active and government spending is at its minimum. On the other hand, the relation between indicators of democracy and the structure of taxation has so far received less

attention, and in this case to the empirical literature has not reached an overall consensus on the sign of these links. Mulligan et al. (2004) find that democracies have flatter personal income tax structures and a generally lower tax revenue/GDP than nondemocracies.

Wintrobe (1990) suggests that democratic countries, since they do not use repressive measures as governing instruments, have to design tax systems that induce more voluntary tax compliance (see also de Juan et al., 1994; Pommerehne and Weck-Hannemann, 1996; Alm, 1996; Feld and Frey, 2002).

Many authors have argued for a positive relationship between tax and democracy as they have seen tax as a function of state-society relations. The existence of a fiscal bargain at the heart of the relationship between citizens and rulers has been demonstrated in cross country regression analysis (Ross, 2004); using citizen surveys (Fjeldstad, 2004); and experimental methods (Cummings et al, 2005). As democracy alters state-society relations, and taxation is a function of this relationship, it is hypothesized that democracy should have an effect on tax outcomes. Since the changes wrought on state-society relations by democracy are positive – opening political space for opposition, giving citizens more voice, creating mechanisms of accountability, and placing constraints on rulers - its impact on taxation should also be positive.

In this paper, we examine effect of tax revenue on democracy. For this purpose, we use three groups of countries that are classified by the index of democracy. And we use annual data covering 2006 to 2011 periods for 7 countries in each group and our method is panel data. Our results are different in each group.

Data description:

In this study, we use annual data for 21 countries during the period of 2006 to 2008, containing democracy index, tax revenue (% GDP) and other revenue except tax (% GDP). Tax revenue and other revenue are obtained from World Bank Database.

But the democracy index should be calculated. There is in fact a large debate among political scientists on the exact definition of what constitutes a democracy. In this article, we used

the democracy index is an index compiled by EIU¹. As described in the report, the democracy index is a weighted average based on answers of 60 questions. The questions are distributed in the five categories: electoral process and pluralism, civil liberties, functioning of government, political participation, and political culture.² According to this measure, each country is a number between zero to ten in terms of democracy. In addition to a numeric score and a ranking, the index categorizes countries as one of three regime full democracies, mean democracies and low democracies.

Based on this classification, there are 7 countries in each group.

In table (1) we show the countries used in article.

Table (1): list of countries

High democracy	Mean democracy	Low democracy
Canada	Russia	Iran
Uk	Venezuela	Algeria
Norway	Indonesia	Qatar
USA	Turkey	Nigeria
Netherland	Brazil	Kazakhstan
Denmark	India	Kuwait
Germany	Malaysia	China

In below, we show the average of tax revenue in each group in figure 1.

Figure (1): the average of tax revenue

As shown, the average tax revenue in the first group of countries with high democracy index is significantly higher than the other two groups.

¹ . Economist Intelligence Unit

² . www.eiu.com

Results:

We estimate panel data model for each groups:

$$Dem_{it} = \beta_{1it} + \beta_{2it}Tax_{it} + \beta_{3it}Rev_{it} + e_{it} \quad (1)$$

Where, Dem_{it} is Democracy index, Tax_{it} is tax revenues and Rev_{it} is other revenues except tax so that tax and rev are percentage of GDP.

In first step, we test the stationary of variable with Levin, Li and Chu and Im, Pesaran and Shim tests that are shown in the tables below:

Table (1): result of stationary test for group one (high democracy)

		Dem	Tax	Rev
Levin, Li and Chu	statistics	-3.766	-1.309	-1.538
	Prob	0.00	0.09	0.06
Im, Pesaran and Shim	statistics	-1.873	-1.285	-0.985
	Prob	0.30	0.47	0.66
		Stationary	Stationary	Stationary

Table (2): result of stationary test for group two (mean democracy)

		Dem	Tax	Rev
Levin, Li and Chu	statistics	-1.909	-4.342	-6.396
	Prob	0.02	0.00	0.00
Im, Pesaran and Shim	statistics	-1.951	01.864	-2.218
	Prob	0.64	0.30	0.56
		Stationary	Stationary	Stationary

Table (3): result of stationary test for group three (low democracy)

		Dem	Tax	Rev
Levin, Li and Chu	statistics	-3.59	-3.294	-2.608
	Prob	0.00	0.00	0.00
Im, Pesaran and Shim	statistics	-1.775	-2.207	-1.815
	Prob	0.36	0.14	0.67
		Stationary	Stationary	Stationary

Then, we estimate the main model for each group. The results are shown in table 4, 5 and 6:

Table (4): result of estimating of high democracy

	C	Tax	Rev
Coefficient	7.949	0.033	0.24
Prob	0.00	0.00	0.07
$R^2 = 0.32$			
$prob(F - statistic) = 0.05$			

For this group, we estimate pooling method by apply F limer test.

In high democracy countries, tax revenue is significant and positive effect on democracy. Also the coefficient of other revenues is significant and positive. In other words, by one percent increase in tax and revenue, the democracy increases 0.033 and 0.024 percent, respectively.

The results showed, both revenues (tax and other revenues) can increase democracy. Because government in high democracy countries is responsible to the people and is no matter where the income is earned.

Table (5): result of estimating of mean democracy

	C	Tax	Rev
Coefficient	5.657	0.058	-0.04
Prob	0.00	0.01	0.02
$R^2 = 0.22$			
$prob(F - statistic) = 0.00$			

In this group, we used random effect method because null hypothesis of Hasman test is not rejected.

The results showed coefficient of tax and revenue are significant. The interpretation of these coefficients are estimated that one percent increase in tax revenue, democracy is 58 percent increase and one percent increase in revenue of government (except tax revenue) is reduce 40 percent of democracy.

According to results, in this country, when governments receive tax from citizen, they should response to them about affairs of country. Then democracy increase in these countries. In contrast, other revenues except tax can increase government power and then they have not responsibility to the citizen.

Table (6): result of estimating of low democracy

	C	Tax	Rev
Coefficient	2.447	-.027	0.065
Prob	0.00	0.108	0.00
$R^2 = 0.85$			
$prob(F - statistic) = 0.00$			

The final group, we used fixed effect method because null hypothesis of Hasman test is rejected.

The results showed coefficient of tax and revenue are significant. The interpretation of these coefficients are estimated that one percent increase in tax revenue, democracy is 27 percent decrease and one percent increase in revenue of government (except tax revenue) increase 6 percent of democracy.

According to results, in this country, government have high power. So government does not participate citizen in the affairs of the country.

Conclusion:

By using panel data method for 21 countries in three groups with high, average and low democracy index, in this article, we analyze the effect of tax revenues on democracy index. Hence, by using annual data for 2006 to 2011, we estimate three models.

In high democracy of countries, tax revenues have positive effect on democracy index. Then

in these countries, citizens have high power in country's decisions.

In mean democracy countries, tax revenues have positive effect on democracy index, as well as. But other revenues except tax have negative effect on democracy index. These results show citizens have power in decisions countries, if they pay tax to government.

And finally, in low democracy of countries. Tax revenues have negative effect on democracy. This result is against of theory. Our interpretation of these results is that the government of such countries have so power and citizens have no interference in the affairs of the country.

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